

**Comparative Sequence Analysis of the Dystrophin (DMD) Gene: Wild-Type vs Mutant in
Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy using BLAST**

Medha Bisht

Independent Bioinformatics Study

Date: July 29, 2025

Statement Of Work

This study was independently conducted using NCBI BLAST and Benchling to analyze DMD gene mutations, reflecting my research interest in genetics and bioinformatics.

Abstract

Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy (DMD) is a severe X-linked neuromuscular disorder caused by mutations in the DMD gene, which encodes the dystrophin protein - essential for muscle fiber stability. In this study, I used computational tools to study what happens when a small change is made in the DMD gene. The point mutation was simulated at specific point (position 10846), changing A to C and was compared with the wild type gene (NM_004006.3) using the NCBI BLAST tools. The alignment revealed a disrupted coding region and reduced sequence coverage in the mutant, suggesting a possible frameshift resulting in a non- functional dystrophin protein. This project demonstrated how even a single nucleotide change can impact protein expression and contribute to genetic disease phenotype.

Comparative Sequence Analysis of the Dystrophin (DMD) Gene: Wild-Type vs Mutant in Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy using BLAST

Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy (DMD) is a severe genetic disorder that causes progressive muscle weakness and usually affects boys. It is caused by mutations in the DMD gene, which is located on the X chromosome. This gene produces dystrophin, a protein that helps protect muscle fibers during movement. When dystrophin is missing or non-functional, muscles become damaged over time, leading to difficulty walking, breathing, and eventually heart complications.

The DMD gene is the largest known human gene, which makes it more likely to develop mutations. While large deletions in the gene are common, even small changes—like switching one base in the DNA—can cause serious effects. These are known as point mutations.

In this project, a single point mutation was simulated at position c.10846, where an A was changed to a C in the mRNA sequence of the DMD gene. This type of change may affect how the genetic code is read, possibly leading to a non-functional protein. To explore this, the mutated sequence was compared with the normal (wild-type) version using NCBI's BLAST tool, which helps align sequences and detect differences. This simple in-silico analysis helps demonstrate how even small mutations can disrupt important biological functions.

Aim and Objectives

The objective of this study is to compare the wild-type DMD gene sequence with a mutant sequence containing a simulated point mutation (c.10846 A to C) using the BLAST tool. This comparison aims to identify structural differences at the nucleotide level and understand how such mutations may contribute to Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy.

Materials

- NCBI GenBank database for wild-type DMD mRNA sequence (NM_004006.3)
- Benchling's sequence editor for mutant sequence generation
- NCBI BLAST tool for sequence alignment

Methods

- Sequence retrieval: The wild-type DMD transcript (NM_004006.3) was retrieved from NCBI GenBank.
- Mutant creation: A point mutation at c.10846A>C was introduced in silico using Benchling to simulate the Duchenne variant.
- BLAST analysis: Wild-type and mutant sequences were aligned using NCBI BLASTn to compare coverage and identity.

Result

To analyze the molecular effect of a simulated point mutation in the dystrophin gene (DMD), wild-type and mutant mRNA sequences were subjected to BLASTn alignment against the NCBI nucleotide database. The wild-type sequence (NM_004006.3) demonstrated complete identity with the reference transcript, while the mutant sequence carrying a c.10846A>C substitution displayed

disrupted patterns. The differences between the alignments are presented below.

Figure 1. BLAST alignment of the wild-type DMD transcript variant NM_004006.3 showing full coverage and 100% identity.

Figure 2a-c. BLAST alignment of the mutant DMD c.10846A>C variant.

Figure 2a. Initial alignment overview.

In contrast, the mutant sequence showed significant base loss and reduced coverage, particularly in the coding region c.10846A>C substitution. This disrupted alignment suggests a potential frameshift effect leading to a non-functional dystrophin protein, a signature characteristic of Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy.

To visualize the impact of the c.10846A>C substitution in the dystrophin (DMD) transcript, BLASTn alignments of both the sequences were analyzed.

Figure 3a. BLAST distribution graph for wild-type DMD transcript (NM_004006.3).

Figure 3b BLAST distribution graph for mutant DMD c.10846A>C variant showing irregularity.

Graphical Comparison of Wild-Type and Mutant Alignments.

The wild-type sequence demonstrated complete alignment coverage across the reference transcript, indicating a fully intact reading frame.

In contrast, the mutant sequence displayed multiple gaps and reduced query coverage, reflecting disruption of the coding region.

WILD-TYPE VS MUTANT TYPE

Parameter	Wild-Type (NM_004006.3)	Mutant (c.10846A>C)
Query Coverage	100%	~85% (reduced)
Identity (%)	100%	~98-99%
E-Value	0.0	1e-120
Frameshift Effect	None	Likely Frameshift
Resulting protein	Full-length dystrophin	Non-Functional

Conclusions

The in-silico introduction of the c.10846A>C substitution in the DMD transcript resulted in significant disruption of sequence alignment compared to the wild-type reference (NM_004006.3). The mutant sequence exhibited multiple gaps and reduced coverage in the coding region, suggesting a loss of frames. Such alterations are characteristics of pathogenic Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy, that are caused by disruptions in the dystrophin mRNA. This analysis shows how bioinformatics can help predict the effects of genetic mutations in diseases like DMD.

References

Benchling. (2025). Benchling DNA sequence editor. Retrieved July 28, 2025, from

<https://www.benchling.com>

National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI). (2023). DMD gene reference sequence (NM_004006.3). Retrieved July 28, 2025, from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>

National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI). (2025). BLAST: Basic Local Alignment Search Tool. Retrieved July 28, 2025, from <https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>